

LEADERSHIP AND CREATIVITY DETERMINANT FOR SUCCESSFUL ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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Skills covered: leadership, teamwork, creativity

Estimated number of lectures / teaching sessions needed: 8
academic hours for undergraduate level students

This module will be applied within an academic course of
undergraduate level in lectures and seminars “Practical
entrepreneurship I” .

Aim: to develop leadership, team work and creativity skills as determinant for successful entrepreneurship and innovations

Brief Abstract: in very changing business environment and increasing competition, students need to develop entrepreneurial skills that are essential for start-up creation and business development. Students will gain business knowledge and work on entrepreneurship skills using various methods in order to be prepared for setting up their own business and become creative leaders of their teams

Methods applied: small group discussions, brain storming, case studies, trait evaluation, tests, interviews and presentations

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1. PERSONALITY TRAITS ESSENTIAL FOR SUCCESSFUL ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP DNA.

are the entrepreneur's success determinants static or changing factors?

Quite often we think that entrepreneur and entrepreneurship skills are something new and discussed just in latest decades, but this issue has been important already while ago. For example Richard Cantillon in 1755 analyses entrepreneurs work in uncertain environment thus it is important to have ability to risk (Balabkins, 2002). John Stuart Mill and Alfred Marshall century later already stress the mass production characteristics and importance of skills for production organisation and management. Joseph Schumpeter at the beginning of 20th century describes entrepreneur as creative, personality with ability to innovate (Bikse, 2003). Already later in 20th century researchers outline other skills like motivation for success (McClland, 1965), goal setting and constant improvement and development (Begley & Boyd, 1987, Rosendahl, Sloof, Van Praag, 2014). In 20th century entrepreneurial ability, entrepreneur and entrepreneurship is defined as forth resource of production (Bikze, Rivza, 2014).

The skills that are required by entrepreneurs fall into three distinct categories (Henry, 2005)

- technical skills,
- business management skills,
- personal entrepreneurial skills.

Technical skills include written and oral communication, technical management, and organizing skills. Business management skills are managerial skills like planning, decision making marketing and accounting. Entrepreneurs also should have personal skills such as innovation, risk taking, and persistence (Elmuti, Khoury, Omran, 2012).

entrepreneurs are born or made?

In business education process quite often we have questions :

- Entrepreneur – is it something we are already by birth or is it something we can become during a life time?
- Entrepreneurs – are they all similar or they are different people with different range of personalities and temperaments?
- Entrepreneurship skills – is it a certain fixed skills that have all successful entrepreneurs or it could differ?
- Do entrepreneurs have a different genetic makeup?

Still we can conclude that personality traits and skills can be learned, it just takes different time for different people. Most important before decision what kind of skills needs to be learned additionally (see Table 1.1.) is to clarify – what kind of personality traits and skills you already have.

Table 1.1. Entrepreneurial skills and abilities in the entrepreneurial process (Chell, 2013)

Behaviour/skills	Expert term	Research source
Innovative/creative ability to generate novel ideas; ability to envision possibilities	Creativity/imagination/vision/foresight	Amabile (1983, 1990), Ardichvili <i>et al.</i> (2003), Csikszentmihalyi (1996), Hills <i>et al.</i> (1997), Locke (2000), Locke and Baum (2007), Rubenson and Runco (1992), Sternberg (2003), Sternberg and Lubart (1995, 1996), Kirton (1976, 1980)
Recognition of opportunity and ability to work out the means-end framework	Alertness; counterfactual thinking	Baron (2000); Gaglio (1997, 2004); Gaglio and Katz (2001), Kirzner (1979, 1997), Shane (2000, 2003)
Identification of opportunity; ability to perceive patterns in information in a given environment	Tacit knowledge; pattern recognition; prototyping	Amit <i>et al.</i> (1993), Nightingale (1998), Baron (2004), Frese (2007), Marsili (2002)
Awareness of factors conducive to opportunity exploitation Prior knowledge pertinent to identification of opportunity; including the ability to acquire further information about a potential opportunity; domain knowledge and associated skills	Veridical perception, interpretation, and discernment Absorptive capacity Domain knowledge	Gaglio (2004), Gaglio and Katz (2001), Kirzner (1979) Cohen and Levinthal (1990), Shane (2000, 2003), Amabile (1983, 1990), Ardichvili <i>et al.</i> (2003), Sigrist (1999), Zucker <i>et al.</i> (1998)
Recognition of social need/ market need Ability to garner necessary material resources	Social/market knowledge Prior knowledge Resourcefulness	Ardichvili <i>et al.</i> (2003), Harper (1996), Shane (2000, 2003) Brush <i>et al.</i> (2001), Stevenson <i>et al.</i> (1985, 1989), Timmons (1989), Wu (1989)
Ability to convince others of value of opportunity Self-belief, self-awareness and ability exert influence and create change	Persuasiveness; social skill; leadership Self-efficacy	Jack and Anderson (2002), McClelland (1987), Witt (1998) Bandura (1997, 1999), Boyd and Vozikis (1994), Chen <i>et al.</i> (1998), Krueger and Brazeal (1994), Markman <i>et al.</i> (2002, 2005)
Trust in own judgement; trusting	Self-confidence; trust Over-confidence	Chandler and Jansen (1992), Chell and Tracey (2005), Locke (2000), Busenitz and Barney (1997), Simon <i>et al.</i> (2000)
Ability to manage other people	Interpersonal skill; leadership	Baron and Markman (2003), Witt (1998)
Ability to differentiate amongst opportunities/information	Judgement	Casson (1982), Chell (2008), Frese (2007), Gaglio and Katz (2001)
Ability to manage risk and shoulder responsibilities in conditions of uncertainty	Risk-propensity; responsibility	Christiansen and Bower (1996), Harper (1996), Hoy and Carland (1983), Miner and Raju (2004), Timmons <i>et al.</i> (1985)

Table 1.1. continued .Entrepreneurial skills and abilities in the entrepreneurial process

Behaviour/skills	Expert term	Research source
Networking and social embedding	Social competence; networking capability	Aldrich and Whetton (1981), Aldrich and Zimmer (1986), Ardichvili <i>et al.</i> (2003), Baron and Markman (2003), Birley (1985), Chell and Baines (2000), Jack and Anderson (2002), Johannisson (1995)
Ability to overcome institutional and other constraints	Political astuteness	Baron and Markman (2003), Harper (1996)
Ability to learn the “rules” and make the right move at the right time	Social learning; adeptness	Argyris and Schoen (1978), Bandura (1997, 1999), Chell (2008)
Ability to endure and cope with difficulties	Resilience	Shapero (1975), Rabow <i>et al.</i> (1983)
Able to apply appropriate skills associated with different stages of business and drive its development forward	Multi-skilled: flexibility; dynamic capabilities	Amit <i>et al.</i> (1990), Davidsson and Honig (2003), McClelland (1987), Timmons <i>et al.</i> (1985), Zahra <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Ability to develop an idea as commercial opportunity, applying the appropriate resources; ability to plan and think ahead	Business acumen; business planning	Arrow (1974), Chandler and Hanks (1994), Frese (2007), Stevenson and Jarillo (1990), Venkataraman (1997), Wu (1989)
Able to go the distance, energetic, motivation and effort expended	Commitment, stamina, energy, effort, motivation, achievement motivation, passion	Timmons <i>et al.</i> (1985), Bird (1989), Boyd and Vozikis (1994), Baum <i>et al.</i> (2001), Baum and Locke (2004a), Locke and Baum (2007), McClelland (1961), Miner <i>et al.</i> (1989), Naffziger <i>et al.</i> (1994)
Able to grow and sustain the enterprise	Strategic competence	Reynolds (1987), Reynolds and White (1997)
Decision-making capability	Decision making; problem formulation and diagnostic skills	Casson (1982, 1995), Schwenck (1988), Schenkel <i>et al.</i> (2009), Wu (1989)

what type of entrepreneur is in your “DNA”?

There are different typologies of entrepreneurs that could be more useful for different enterprises of industries and specific tasks that need to be achieved.

In some sense, and in varying degrees, every human being has the DNA to become an entrepreneur. Setting goals, having dreams, and casting visions are all activities included in the realm of the entrepreneur. In this sense every human has an entrepreneurial DNA, so we believe there is an entrepreneur inside everyone - and that inner entrepreneur is not a one-size-fits-all entrepreneur. Still there are more and less successful entrepreneurs.

The most important is to know what are your particular traits and characteristics in order to determine your strength as well as traits that you need to work on and develop.

Quite well-known is the BOSI DNA system (Abraham, 2011) – via certain tests you determine what type (or combinations of typologies) a person has Builder, Opportunist, Specialist or Innovator DNA.

Builder: Strategic, always looking for the upper hand. Talent: creating scalable business ventures. If you're a builder, you're all about creating a business from scratch. You're focused and driven, and will do anything to help your business succeed. You sacrifice time and money to make that happen (sometimes to your family's chagrin). You're a great salesperson, and work to motivate your team to be as enthusiastic about the company as you is.

Opportunist: Speculative, always in the right place at the right time. Talent: making money fast. As an opportunist, you're great at seeing the potential of an idea or a business. You want to make money quickly, and aren't interested in nurturing your business for any other reason. People who flip houses or invest in IPOs are usually considered opportunists. You don't want to work all your life (or even right now) but you recognize that you have to make your business succeed in order to relax on a beach somewhere.

Specialist: Focused, in it for the long term. Talent: providing exceptional client service. Specialists get into business because they have extensive knowledge and interest in a particular field. Running a business helps them help other people. They're not in business to make millions, but rather because they can do what they love every day for years. Specialists aren't aggressive about sales, and may have trouble differentiating themselves from other specialists.

Innovator: Inventive, with a desire to make an impact. Talent: creating game-changing products. If you constantly have great ideas that you're able to turn into businesses, you're an innovator. Running a business probably isn't your number one goal in life, but your great idea may have propelled you into entrepreneurship on its own. Scientists and inventors are innovators. You may prefer to hide out in the lab to actually managing the day-to-day activities a business owner is responsible for.

Filling good entrepreneurship tests helps you understand what motivates you and how you work well with other people that are essential for successful entrepreneurship.

Task Entrepreneurs DNA

Fill the test and read about your BOSI entrepreneur DNA type

<https://www.bosidna.com/discover>

Check-up tasks

- What kind of personality traits are necessary for entrepreneur?

2. THE VALUE OF CREATIVITY AND INNOVATION IN ENTREPRENEURSHIP.

is there a space for new start-up in oversaturated global market?

We live in the century with large global competition, transnational corporations and the situation where supply exceeds demand. We look to statistical data on huge number of companies, on big scale of short time start-ups and quite often we have a question – is it possible to survive in this global competition for new business attempt?

2.1. Blue Ocean strategy – breaking away from the competition to value innovation

blue or red?

Using symbols of Blue Ocean Strategy by W. Chan Kim, Renee Mauborgn – this is so called red ocean strategy (Chan Kim, Mauborgn, 2005). The colour red is used to describe dramatic competition – sharks swimming around and fighting to blood. Red oceans will always matter and will always be a fact of business life but starting your enterprise you can choose to use a strategy of blue ocean – ocean of essentially different enterprises that offer innovative products (see Table 2.1.). Competition-based red ocean strategy assumes that an industry’s structural conditions are given and that firms are forced to compete within them, an assumption based on what the academics call the structuralist view, or environmental determinism. In contrast, value innovation is based on the view that market boundaries and industry structure are not given and can be reconstructed by the actions and beliefs of particular industry players.

Table 2.1. Characteristics of Red and Blue ocean strategy (Chan Kim, Mauborgn, 2005).

Red Ocean Strategy	VS	Blue Ocean Strategy
Compete in existing market space.		Create uncontested market space.
Beat the competition.		Make the competition irrelevant .
Exploit existing demand.		Create and capture new demand.
Make the value-cost trade-off.		Break the value-cost trade-off.
Align the whole system of a firm’s activities with its strategic choice of differentiation or low cost .		Align the whole system of a firm’s activities in pursuit of differentiation and low cost .

Blue oceans denote all the industries not in existence today—the unknown market space, untainted by competition. In blue oceans, demand is created rather than fought over. There is ample opportunity for growth that is both profitable and rapid. There are two ways to create blue oceans. In a few cases, companies can give rise to completely new industries, but in most cases, a blue ocean is created from within a red ocean when a company alters the boundaries of an existing industry.

Creators of blue oceans, in sharp contrast to companies playing by traditional rules, never use the competition as a benchmark. Instead they make it irrelevant by creating a leap in value for both buyers and the company itself. The most important feature of blue ocean strategy is that it rejects the fundamental tenet of conventional strategy: that a trade-off exists between value and cost. According to this thesis, companies can either create greater value for customers at a higher cost or create reasonable value at a lower cost. In other words, strategy is essentially a choice between differentiation and low cost. But when it comes to creating blue oceans, the evidence shows that successful companies pursue differentiation and low cost simultaneously. By driving down costs while simultaneously driving up value for buyers, a company can achieve a leap in value for both itself and its customers. Since buyer value comes from the utility and price a company offers, and a company generates value for itself through cost structure and price, blue ocean strategy is achieved only when the whole system of a company's utility, price, and cost activities is properly aligned (see Figure 2.1.). It is this whole-system approach that makes the creation of blue oceans a sustainable strategy. Blue ocean strategy integrates the range of a firm's functional and operational activities.

Figure 2.1. Value Innovation is the Cornerstone of Blue Ocean Strategy (Chan Kim, Mauborgn, 2005).

Value innovation means that instead of focusing on beating the competition, entrepreneurs focus on making the competition irrelevant by creating a leap in value for buyers and your company, thereby opening up new and uncontested market space.

2.2. Innovations and creativeness skills

Skill: creativity

innovation and entrepreneurship demand creativity

Creativity is marked by the ability to create, bring into existence, to invent into a new form, to produce through imaginative skill, to make to bring into existence something new. Creativity is not ability to create out of nothing (only God can do that), but the ability to generate new ideas by combining, changing, or reapplying existing ideas. Some creative ideas are astonishing and brilliant, while others are just simple, good practical ideas that no one seems to have thought, of yet (Okpara, 2007).

Task Problem solving.

Students need to choose one entrepreneurship related problem, for example one specific product selling process and channels.

Student or group of students need to write down the most crazy, ridiculous problem solutions they can think of. The crazier and sometimes seeming impossible - the better. After about 10-15 minutes, student needs to forget about being crazy and zoom back to normality and get on with solving their problems and be practical. They need to examine each of their crazy ideas to see what more practical solution it may suggest. They do not need to think of idea as crazy idea, but do the best they can from the ideas that are generated.

Check-up tasks

- Characterise red ocean strategy.
- Characterise blue ocean strategy.

3. TEAM LEADER MOTIVATION AND COMMUNICATION SKILLS.

3.1. Leader and leadership of 21st century

Skill: leadership

Every future entrepreneur and current business owner wants to be a good leader, but how can you be a good leader if you don't know what leadership really is? There is no single definition what is meant by good leader that is why you need to look through different perspectives to leader and leadership.

Task Stand by your quote

Students need to read each of the quotes and have to chose and stand by one quote that resonates well with their personal views on what makes a good leader.

Leadership quotes (Kevin Kruse “ 365 Best Inspirational Quotes: Daily Motivation For Your Best Year Ever” , Wholehearted Leadership Press, 2014, 116 p)

- A leader is best when people barely know he exists, when his work is done, his aim fulfilled, they will say: we did it ourselves. —Lao Tzu
- You manage things; you lead people. —Rear Admiral Grace Murray Hopper
- The first responsibility of a leader is to define reality. The last is to say thank you. In between, the leader is a servant. —Max DePree
- Leadership is the capacity to translate vision into reality. —Warren Bennis
- Before you are a leader, success is all about growing yourself. When you become a leader, success is all about growing others. —Jack Welch
- A leader is a dealer in hope. —Napoleon Bonaparte
- A leader is one who knows the way, goes the way, and shows the way. —John Maxwell
- Leadership is having a vision, sharing that vision and inspiring others to support your vision while creating their own. – Mindy Gibbins-Klein, founder of REAL Thought Leaders
- My own definition of leadership is this: The capacity and the will to rally men and women to a common purpose and the character which inspires confidence. —General Montgomery
- Leadership is lifting a person’s vision to high sights, the raising of a person’s performance to a higher standard, the building of a personality beyond its normal limitations. —Peter Drucker
- Never doubt that a small group of thoughtful, concerned citizens can change world. Indeed it is the only thing that ever has. —Margaret Mead
- The nation will find it very hard to look up to the leaders who are keeping their ears to the ground. —Sir Winston Churchill
- The most dangerous leadership myth is that leaders are born—that there is a genetic factor to leadership. That’s nonsense; in fact, the opposite is true. Leaders are made rather than born. —Warren Bennis
- To command is to serve, nothing more and nothing less. —Andre Malraux
- He who has never learned to obey cannot be a good commander. —Aristotle
- Become the kind of leader that people would follow voluntarily; even if you had no title or position. —Brian Tracy

- I start with the premise that the function of leadership is to produce more leaders, not more followers. —Ralph Nader
- Effective leadership is not about making speeches or being liked; leadership is defined by results not attributes. —Peter Drucker
- A great person attracts great people and knows how to hold them together. —Johann Wolfgang Von Goethe
- The best executive is the one who has sense enough to pick good men to do what he wants done, and self-restraint enough to keep from meddling with them while they do it. —Theodore Roosevelt
- Leadership is influence. —John C. Maxwell
- You don't lead by pointing and telling people some place to go. You lead by going to that place and making a case. —Ken Kesey
- Men make history and not the other way around. In periods where there is no leadership, society stands still. Progress occurs when courageous, skilful leaders seize the opportunity to change things for the better. —Harry S. Truman
- People buy into the leader before they buy into the vision. —John Maxwell

There are different perspectives to what is meant by leader and leadership. Of course we can classify leaders using different perspectives.

As classic and simple approach for leader typology we can use psychologist Kurt Lewin (Lewin, 1939) in which he provided the foundation of many of the approaches that followed afterwards. He argued that there are three major styles of leadership – autocratic, democratic and Laissez-faire.

Autocratic leaders make decisions without consulting their team members, even if their input would be useful. This can be appropriate when you need to make decisions quickly, when there's no need for team input, and when team agreement isn't necessary for a successful outcome. However, this style can be demoralizing, and it can lead to high levels of absenteeism and staff turnover.

Democratic leaders make the final decisions, but they include team members in the decision-making process. They encourage creativity, and people are often highly engaged in projects and decisions. As a result, team members tend to have high job satisfaction and high productivity. This is not always an effective style to use, though, when you need to make a quick decision.

Laissez-faire leaders give their team members a lot of freedom in how they do their work, and how they set their deadlines. They provide support with resources and advice if needed, but otherwise they don't get involved. This autonomy can lead to high job satisfaction, but it can be damaging if team members don't manage their time well, or if they don't have the knowledge, skills, or self motivation to do their work effectively. (Laissez-faire leadership can also occur when managers don't have control over their work and their people.)

Quite often the proper leadership style depends on the situation of enterprise faces and on the person traits and values, so mainly there are three basic factors that also influence which leadership style to use.

First of all manager's personal background - personality, knowledge, values, ethics, and experiences does the manager have. Second - the characteristics of employees being supervised. Employees are individuals with different personalities and backgrounds. And the third - the enterprise of organisation itself. The traditions, values, philosophy, and concerns of the company will influence how a manager acts.

To be a good leader, you'll need to fortify yourself by keeping up with the latest leadership trends, observing other leaders (including leaders in your own chain of command and leaders in the news), and recognizing that your own unique brand of leadership will change as you gain experience.

It is important is to learn from those that are recognised as good leaders.

Each entrepreneur has his or her own specific set of methods of leadership therefore entrepreneurship skill development can be achieved by exchanging information about the methods that are used by other to achieve certain goals.

Task Leadership skill exchange interview with students “My experience in student teams”

Task objective is to encourage students to talk to one another and exchange their experience about leadership skills and best practices that they have used when being part of student group/team in their previous study period.

Students need to sign up the names of three other student cards. Then till the next class students seek out their students to conduct a “My experience in student teams” interview. During the study period every student have different group tasks and have been part of several different student teams. Students need to characterise their behaviour in these teams and ask following questions:

- How do you motivate other students in your team to fulfil the group tasks?
- How do you track changes what is done and needs to be done?
- How do you maintain your student team member focus on subject and specific goals that are set by team?
- How do you set, clarify, and hold your reports accountable to your expectations?
- How do you recognize successful work?

Discussion. After the tasks students need to share student team leadership tips and discuss what could be applied in entrepreneurship.

3.2. Need for team motivation and team work

Skill: Team building

In previous chapter we talked about leadership still we can not talk just about the leadership itself without the people and teams as leadership involves more than one person. It is not possible to be a leader without a group of people following your direction and putting their trust in their leader and his/her vision. Remember, as a leader you have a responsibility to your employees, group, organization, or team to lead fairly and ethically.

Team building skills are critical for your effectiveness of entrepreneur. And even if you are not yet entrepreneur, better understanding of team work can make you a more effective student or employee in your current path.

How we can measure team success - team building success is when the team can accomplish something much bigger and work more effectively than a group of the same individuals working on their own. It means - you have a synergy of individual contributions.

Poor communication lies at the root of many team problems. It can lead to mistakes, quality problems, conflict, missed deadlines, and lost opportunities. That's why it can often pay to help people develop their in-team communication skills. To be able to work with team it is important to be able to communicate in the way teams' members understand. Next training can help to improve communication skills.

Task Back-to-Back Drawing

Divide your group into pairs or three people group, and have each group sit on the floor two people back to back and another one could be in front of second person. First person in each group is given a simple picture, and give the other persons a pencil and pad of paper.

Ask the people holding the pictures to give verbal instructions to their partners on how to draw the shape – without actually telling the partners what the shape is. After they've finished, ask each group to compare their original shape with the actual drawing, and consider the following questions: How well did the first person describe the shape? How well did the second person interpret the instructions? Were there problems with both the sending and receiving parts of the communication process?

Discussion

Students need to discuss about communication skill importance in business teams.

In the team building it is important to know and understand the structure of team and member strength.

Task Survival Scenario

This exercise forces the team to communicate and agree to ensure their 'survival.' Teams is informed that their airplane has just crashed in the ocean. There's a desert island nearby, and there's room on the lifeboat for every person – plus 12 items they'll need to survive on the island. Team needs to choose which items they want to take. How do they decide? How do they rank or rate each item?

Task Mine field

This is a great exercise if you have a large room or outdoor field. Set up a 'mine field' using chairs, balls, cones, boxes, or any other object that could potentially be an obstacle and trip someone up. Leave enough space between the objects for someone to walk through.

Next, divide your group into pairs. Pay attention to who you match with whom. This is a perfect opportunity to work on relationships, so you might want to put together people who have trust issues with each other.

Blindfold one person, the 'mine walker', this person is not allowed to talk. Ask his or her partner to stay outside the mine field, and give verbal directions, helping the mine walker avoid the obstacles, and reach the other side of the area.

Before you begin, allow partners a few minutes to plan how they'll communicate. Then, make sure there are consequences when people hit an obstacle. For example, perhaps they have to start again from the beginning.

Team building skills allow entrepreneur to gain collaborative advantage.

Collaboration in enterprise is when two or more people (often groups or project teams) work together through idea sharing and thinking to accomplish a common goal. With the changes and advancements in technology, such as high speed internet, web-based programs, file sharing, email and video-conferencing, collaboration has become a more productive way of doing things. Collaborative advantage comes in to the place when people try to share their knowledge and generate business ideas for common purpose.

Check-up tasks

- Choose one type of leader that you have met and characterise advantages and disadvantages that you noticed.

Home task Successful entrepreneur cognition

Objective is to encourage students to look for information about successful entrepreneurs, choose the one who inspires the most and write conclusions and insights of the entrepreneur skills and leadership methods used.

Activity Description: Each entrepreneur has his or her own specific set of methods of leadership. Entrepreneurship skill development can be achieved by exchanging information about the methods that are used by other to achieve certain goals.

Students need to choose one internationally recognised successful entrepreneur and write 3 pages of conclusions and insights of the entrepreneur skills and leadership methods used by this person. The entrepreneurs can be chosen from the list The 25 Most Influential Business Leaders Of 2013 in Business Insider (Stanger, Robinson, 2013).

After writing the 3 pages about the inspiring successful entrepreneur, student needs to choose one skill that he/she would like to improve and write the activities that could be done personally during the next month to improve it.

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